

Two Possibilities For The Masses Equation

O Manor

May 2, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing a varying Lorenz manifold, (M, g_E) with signature $(3,1)$, which is the connected manifold, $M = M_0 \times R$, invoked stationary, by the Euler Lagrange operator. Such a manifold experience arbitrary variations that vanish into matter, some of those vanishing elements experience a symmetry breaking ending in mass attaining, or $8 - (1)$ variations. The rate in which families form is currently unknown, the difference is in additional factor of $\frac{1}{9}$. Both variations of the equation agree on the mass of the fourth family, 0.113 Mev, about 56 times lighter than first family total mass. Such a series could agree with dark matter, and solve the question of arbitrary amount of families.

Introduction

[1.9]

[1320]

[172,770]

[4.4]

[87]

[4240]

Combine the masses according to generation:

$$1.9 + 4.4 = 6\frac{1}{3} \quad (1)$$

$$1320 + 87 = 1407 \quad (1.1)$$

$$172,770 + 4240 = 177010 \quad (1.11)$$

Rescale the first by factor of $8 + (1)$ and the third by inverse of $8 + (1)$

$$6\frac{1}{3} * 9 = 57 = 50 + 7 \quad (1.2)$$

$$1320 + 87 = 1407 = 1400 + 7 \quad (1.21)$$

$$\frac{177010}{9} = 19,667 = 19,660 + 7 \quad (1.211)$$

Also, notice:

$$50 * 28 = 1400$$

$$1400 * 14 = 19,660$$

Notice as well:

$$28 = 7 * 4$$

$$14 = 7 * 2$$

So to go from first to second and from second to third

$$(7 * 4) * 50 + (7)$$

$$(7 * 2) * 1400 + (7)$$

In addition, if we go from low to high, it does not make sense physically; it should be Lagrangian oriented nature is dividing by increasing amount to minimize the arbitrary variations, so if correct we should go from three to one by dividing:

$$\frac{19,660 + (7)}{7 * 2} = 1400 + (7) \quad (1.3)$$

$$\frac{1400 + (7)}{7 * 4} = 50 + (7) * \frac{1}{9} \quad (1.31)$$

Next predict that **total mass** for fourth to sixth family's:

$$\frac{50 + (7)}{7 * 8} * \frac{1}{9} = 0.113 \text{ mev} \quad (1.4)$$

$$\frac{0.113}{7 * 16 * 9} = 0.000113 \text{ mev}$$

$$\frac{0.000113}{7 * 32 * 9} = 5.95 * 10^{-8} \text{ mev}$$

We used that original procedure in the thesis. However since the re-scaling factor we artificially put, so we can find the decreasing pattern, a second procedure could be:

$$\frac{0.113}{7 * 16} = 0.00100 \text{ mev}$$

$$\frac{0.00100}{7 * 32} = 0.0000045 \text{ mev}$$

For the fifth and sixth families and the equation of the masses would be:

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{l=1}^r N_E} \quad (2)$$

And not

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{l=1}^r N_E} * \frac{1}{9} \quad (2.1)$$

$$N_E = 2E; \quad E \geq 1$$

It is also unclear whether different families, which occupy the same space would interact with each other. Any particle physicist reading this is welcome to share his ideas regarding those interesting questions. There could be additional possibilities, which take into account that the $8 + (1)$ is varying with time as well. One did not include such options, as they seem to be more complicated. In addition, the reasons for such variations do not arise from the framework. The bottom line is that the masses pattern could take several forms, which one is correct is unclear to the author. Ideas by readers are welcomed. Despite the uncertainties, we face, the overall idea is holding. There should be infinite families forming below first, their total mass converging to zero.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)